

THE ROLE OF WOMEN CENTRIC INSURANCE SCHEMES IN REDUCING POVERTY (SDG-1)

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Abstract

Investing in the well-being and empowerment of women yields long-term dividends for India's future prosperity. When women thrive, they contribute not only to their families' welfare but also to the broader community and economy. Empowered women are more likely to invest in their children's education and health, breaking the cycle of poverty and laying the groundwork for intergenerational success.

The study adopted a descriptive research design, gathering primary data through a structured questionnaire from 400 respondents. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics and chi-square tests. The findings reveal differing levels of awareness among the respondents. This study goes beyond merely identifying the existence of various schemes; it also explores their significance, benefits, and impact on achieving sustainable development goals. The goal is to ensure that education serves as a tool for personal and social development, helping to break cycles of poverty and inequality. The purpose of this study is to close this knowledge gap by examining the awareness of women-centric insurance schemes among women in Coimbatore and determining the relationship between women-centric insurance schemes and sustainable development goals.

Keywords: *Women centric insurance, Women empowerment, Poverty Alleviation, SDG-1 etc.,*

Introduction

Insurance can play a crucial role in preventing large debts among the poor in the event of an emergency (Ali, 2018), which can prevent further impoverishment of poor households. In countries where governments are unable to provide compulsory health insurance or compensate its full cost, reduction in uncompensated health care is among the major problems (Binnendijk et al., 2013). There is a clear trend in the insurance industry toward social and financial inequality (Li, 2020, Liu, 2020). The reason behind this trend is that the poor have far fewer opportunities to take out insurance against various risks than the better-off or the middle class. The emerging

private insurance market cannot provide sufficient financial protection and reach the people most in need of funds (Jin et al., 2016)¹.

In India central and state government provide compulsory insurance schemes to various members, especially insurance schemes designed for the purpose of women empowerment whether supports to attain the goal of sustainable development.

Review of Literature

Liudmila Tsvetkova et al,(2022) conducted a study to identify the relationships and interdependencies between the key financial characteristics of low-income households and their propensity for insurance purchase under the scenario where the insurance product can reduce the likelihood of catastrophic expenses. The study relies on the time series model to analyze statistical information. The findings will be useful to state and municipal employers who develop poverty reduction and/or elimination measures and to academic researchers by opening up new avenues for research.

Antoinette Yaa Benewah et al,(2020) investigate, to explore and assess the role of Micro-insurance in poverty reduction in Ghana. This paper is a qualitative analysis based on three case studies. Non-probability sampling techniques are used for choosing the unit of analysis which resulted in 4 firms (4 managers). Also, data were collected via a questionnaire and an in-depth interview. The study identified that Micro-insurance provides financial support to the poor in the event of a disaster, social protection against disasters and shocks, savings, employment, and as well as enhances asset accumulation among clients. The study found that the lack of innovative micro-insurance product, inadequate distribution channels, the lack of supportive micro-insurance legal framework, uncompetitive pricing of micro-insurance products, low government support in micro-insurance programs, low-income levels of respondents, the religious or cultural factors influence the demand of insurance products and low public trust are the factors that affect the demand of micro-insurance products. Also, the study found that the development of innovative products, establishing processes that build trust in clients, instituting efficient service delivery channels, documentation should be simplified and the government should support micro-insurance products are the ways to increase patronage of micro-insurance products.

Statement of the Problem

Although India has made great progress in recent years towards women's empowerment and gender equality, enduring socioeconomic gaps nonetheless pose a threat to these gains. Ensuring women have access to financial stability and protection is crucial for addressing these disparities, particularly through women-focused insurance schemes. These programs provide

financial support for various life events, such as childbirth, medical emergencies, and livelihood assistance, aiming to address the unique needs and challenges faced by women. However, the government may not be fully confident about certain following aspects.

1. Are they aware of the various insurance schemes offered by the central and state governments?
2. Do the insurance schemes contribute to advancing key Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)?
3. Is there a connection between these insurance schemes and the broader vision of the Sustainable Development Goals?

Objectives:

To find out the answer for the questions raised in the statement of problem the following objectives were framed. The main objective of this study is to investigate the relationship between women-centric insurance schemes and their contribution to the achievement of sustainable development goals. This objective can guide an in-depth exploration of how insurance schemes align with specific SDGs, such as poverty reduction, gender equality, and economic empowerment, and how they help foster sustainable socio-economic development.

Research Methodology

The research design employed is descriptive research. Descriptive research includes various types of surveys and fact-finding inquiries. The primary goal of descriptive research is to describe the current state of affairs. The study relies on primary data collected via a structured questionnaire.

Sample Design

This study seeks to examine the level of awareness among working women in Coimbatore district regarding women-centric insurance schemes, with an emphasis on contributing to the achievement of reducing poverty/ (SDG-1).

The researcher used a questionnaire to collect data from 400 of the working women in Coimbatore district. The convenience sampling method was used to select the sample respondents; the collected primary data was analyzed using Chi Square test. Secondary information was gathered from magazines, journals, books, government reports, insurance companies, and SDG progress reports.

Hypothesis Testing

- ✓ **H₀**: Women-centric insurance schemes do not have a significant impact on achieving Sustainable Development Goal 1.
- ✓ **H₁**: Women-centric insurance schemes significantly contribute to poverty reduction (SDG 1).

Data Analysis & Interpretation

Awareness on Women Centric Insurance Policies

Table - 1

S,No	Scheme	Extremely Aware	Moderately Aware	Somewhat Aware	Slightly Aware	Not at all Aware
1	Pradhan Mantri Surakshit Matritva Abhiyan (PMSMA)	121	137	104	28	10
2	Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY)	125	127	80	30	32
3	Pradhan Mantri Jeevan Jyoti Bima Yojana (PMJJBY)	148	108	85	51	8
4	Janani Suraksha Yojana (JSY)	71	157	90	54	28
5	Pradhan Mantri Suraksha Bima Yojana (PMSBY)	98	112	115	40	35
6	Muthulakshmi Reddy Maternity Benefit Scheme	110	134	115	28	13
7	Chief Minister's Comprehensive Health Insurance Scheme (CMCHIS)	102	116	88	63	31
8	Ayushman Bharat Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana (PMJAY)	99	130	102	51	18
9	Aam Aadmi Bima Yojana (AABY)	92	143	96	29	40

10	Sukanya Samridhi Yojana (SSY)	93	137	84	68	18
11	Beti Bachao Beti Padhao (BBBP) Scheme	141	124	73	41	21
12	Arignar Anna Free Marriage Assistance Scheme	93	144	94	48	21

Based on the above table 1, which presents data on the awareness levels for various women-centric insurance schemes, the following insights can be drawn

The awareness levels are measured across five categories: "Extremely Aware," "Moderately Aware," "Somewhat Aware," "Slightly Aware," and "Not at all Aware." In Pradhan Mantri Surakshit Matritva Abhiyan (PMSMA) scheme 121 respondents (a significant portion) are extremely aware about this scheme whereas 137 respondents indicating moderately aware about the scheme and only 10 respondents are not at all aware, suggesting that this scheme is well-known among the respondents.

Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY) has a strong level of awareness, with 125 respondents being **extremely aware** and 127 being **moderately aware**. However, a significant portion of respondents (32) are **not at all aware** of the scheme, indicating a need for further outreach. In Pradhan Mantri Jeevan Jyoti Bima Yojana (PMJJBY) shows a high level of awareness, with 148 respondents being extremely aware. Only 8 respondents are not at all aware, indicating widespread familiarity with the scheme.

Janani Suraksha Yojana (JSY): The majority of respondents are **moderately aware** (157), with a smaller group being **Extremely Aware** (71). However, a significant number (28) are **not at all aware**, highlighting the need for enhanced awareness initiatives.

Pradhan Mantri Suraksha Bima Yojana (PMSBY) - Awareness is relatively spread across categories, with 98 respondents being extremely aware and 112 moderately aware. There is a moderate number of people (35) who are not at all aware, which suggests the need for better outreach. In Muthulakshmi Reddy Maternity Benefit Scheme a solid awareness level is evident, with 110 respondents being extremely aware. Only 13 respondents are not at all aware, indicating a broad reach of the scheme. In Chief Minister's Comprehensive Health Insurance Scheme (CMCHIS) 102 respondents are extremely aware, a larger number are only moderately aware (116). A considerable number of respondents (31) are not at all aware, indicating room for further awareness campaigns.

In Ayushman Bharat Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana (PMJAY) scheme awareness is generally strong, with 99 respondents being extremely aware and 130 moderately aware. Only 18 respondents are not at all aware, indicating overall good awareness. In Aam Aadmi Bima Yojana (AABY) scheme a higher percentage of respondents fall into the moderately aware (143) and extremely aware (92) categories. However, 40 respondents are not at all aware, indicating that more awareness efforts might be necessary.

In Sukanya Samridhi Yojana (SSY) there is a relatively balanced distribution of awareness, with 93 respondents being extremely aware and 137 moderately aware. Only 18 respondents are not at all aware of the scheme. In Beti Bachao Beti Padhao (BBBP) Scheme 141 respondents being extremely aware and 124 moderately aware, this scheme enjoys a high level of awareness. Only 21 respondents are not at all aware, indicating its widespread recognition. In Arignar Anna Free Marriage Assistance Scheme The majority are moderately aware (144), with 93 respondents being extremely aware. Only 21 respondents are not at all aware, showing a strong level of awareness.

Overall Interpretation

The majority of respondents across all schemes are either extremely aware or moderately aware, suggesting that women-centric insurance policies have generally high visibility among the population. Overall, most respondents seem to be either Extremely Aware or Moderately Aware of most schemes, with fewer respondents falling into the lower awareness categories ("Slightly Aware" and "Not at all Aware").

Schemes like Pradhan Mantri Jeevan Jyoti Bima Yojana (PMJJBY), Beti Bachao Beti Padhao (BBBP), and Pradhan Mantri Surakshit Matritva Abhiyan (PMSMA) show the highest levels of extreme awareness, indicating effective outreach and communication. However, some schemes, such as Aam Aadmi Bima Yojana (AABY), Janani Suraksha Yojana (JSY), and Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana (PMMVY), have a higher number of respondents who are not at all aware, suggesting that these schemes might require more targeted awareness campaigns to reach the unawakened audience. Overall, the analysis reflects a good level of awareness but highlights areas where efforts could be enhanced to ensure wider knowledge and accessibility of the schemes among women.

Relationship between the Awareness Level of Insurance and the SDG-1 "No Poverty"

- ✓ **H₀:** Women-centric insurance schemes do not have a significant impact on achieving Sustainable Development Goal 1.(No Poverty)

Table - 2

Awareness Level of Insurance * No Poverty Cross tabulation							
Awareness Level of Insurance	No Poverty						Total
	Rank 1	Rank 2	Rank 3	Rank 4	Rank 5	Rank 6	
Low	8	16	10	8	17	18	77
Medium	30	48	39	30	54	44	245
High	11	17	10	9	17	14	78
Total	49	81	59	47	88	76	400

Pearson Chi-Square Test Value: **2.315**

Degrees of Freedom (df): **10**

Asymptotic Significance (2-sided): **0.993**

Based on the provided Chi-Square test results, we can interpret the relationship between the "Awareness Level of Insurance" and "No Poverty" variables as follows:

The above table shows that out of 400 working women 77 have low awareness of insurance, making up approximately 19.25% of the total sample. 245 individuals fall under medium awareness, accounting for 61.25% of the total sample. This is the most common awareness level. 78 individuals have high awareness, constituting about 19.5% of the total sample. Across all ranks of "No Poverty," the majority of respondents fall under the medium awareness category. This suggests that most people, regardless of their 'No Poverty' rank, have a moderate level of awareness about insurance. Both low and high awareness levels are less frequent compared to medium awareness across all ranks. The distribution of low awareness is relatively even across ranks, with a slight increase in Rank 6. High awareness also does not show a distinct pattern, though it appears marginally higher in Rank 2. There is no clear linear trend that higher or lower "No Poverty" ranks are associated with distinct awareness levels. The majority are medium aware across all categories. This lack of a strong trend aligns with the results from the Chi-Square test, where no statistically significant association was found between the 'No Poverty' levels and insurance awareness.

The Pearson Chi-Square value of 2.315 with a significance level (p-value) of 0.993 indicates that there is no statistically significant association between the "Awareness Level of Insurance" and the "No Poverty" variable. All the tests consistently suggest that there is no statistically significant association between the "Awareness Level of Insurance" and the "No Poverty" levels. Given the high p-values across all tests, we fail to reject the null hypothesis,

which posits that there is no relationship between the two variables. This means that changes in the 'No Poverty' classification do not seem to be associated with changes in the awareness level of insurance in a statistically significant way. In summary, the results indicate no meaningful relationship between the two variables, suggesting that 'No Poverty' status does not influence the awareness level of insurance among the individuals surveyed.

Limitations of the Study

- The study was limited to the state of Coimbatore district.
- When conducting surveys, time is of the essence.
- Some respondents may not have provided accurate information, resulting in inaccurate results.

Conclusion:

In summary, our study sheds light on how much women in Coimbatore know about women-centric insurance schemes. The study found that while some women are aware of these schemes, many don't fully understand how they work or how they can benefit. Factors like cost and accessibility also affect whether women use these schemes. It's clear that raising awareness about these insurance options and making them more affordable and accessible could really help women in Coimbatore. When women have access to insurance that meets their needs, it can make a big difference in their lives. They can better handle unexpected expenses and make more informed financial decisions, which can lead to stronger families and communities overall. To make this happen, both state and central Government need to focus on educating women about these insurance options and finding ways to make them more affordable and easier to access.

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